

Anna M. Sitz: *Pagan Inscriptions, Christian Viewers*. The Afterlives of Temples and Their Texts in the Late Antique Eastern Mediterranean. Oxford: Oxford University Press 2023. 352 S., 66 Illustrations (Cultures of Reading in the Ancient Mediterranean 2)

The book under review is an epitome of two research strands which have been very prominently gaining ground during in the last two decades of studies on the Later Roman Empire. One is the exploration of the perception of inscriptions and of the interactions with them by both literate and illiterate people.¹ This can be equalized with reading, viewing, touching, sometimes also sizing or destroying, and a plethora of other activities. As such, the book nicely finds its place in a new OUP series edited by William A. Johnson and Chris Keith, which aims at presenting studies on ancient “reading cultures” very inclusively understood. The author [further S.] is, however, fully aware that reading alone is not enough to describe the interactions with inscriptions and that she needs to transgress far beyond the series’s framework. Here comes the second research trend – the study of spoliation and reuse of architectural elements in Late Antiquity. In fact the book can serve as an introduction to the reuse of public spaces and architecture in as much as it is a close study in epigraphy. As her main study object, S. chose the inscriptions and infrastructure of pre-Christian temples, arguing that these were the “most contested places” in Late Antiquity, also very rich in inscriptions. As a result, the themes of the book very often overlap with general attitudes of Christians to “pagan” buildings or “pagan heritage,” not just to inscriptions.

Although the book draws the evidence from the entire late antique East, from Delphi to the Egyptian temples, S. herself admits that Anatolia gets much more “screen time” than other regions. This disproportion is really visible and derives, not from the fact that western Anatolia was one of the regions with a very rich epigraphic culture (pp. 25–26), but rather from S.’s expert knowledge of this area. This, however, does not diminish the final outcome.

The methodological and conceptual attitudes presented by the author are very mature and well-thought. S. is aware of the complex nature of interactions with inscriptions – already in antiquity some inscriptions were hundred-years old, operated with archaic linguistic and institutional forms, or were composed in languages not always understandable to their late-antique readers. S. attempts to assess the impact which both understandable and meaningless texts could have through their contents, script, appearance, layout, type of support and surroundings. She is also very well-read in literary sources, especially hagiography based on a creative re-telling of information sourced from inscriptions.² Individual episodes from hagiographical works or inquiries into their structure are skillfully used by Sitz to illustrate how inscriptions functioned in the ancient world and how they could be picked up and incorporated by writers. Finally as claimed by the author in the preface, the book is also on “omissions.” It tackles the problem on decisions taken by ancient Christians: which inscriptions should be left intact, which should be modified or displaced.

¹ See, for example, S. Agusta-Boularot, ‘Malalas épigraphiste? Nature et fonction des citations épigraphiques dans la Chronique’, in S. Agusta-Boularot, J. Beaucamp, A.-M. Bernardi, E. Caire (eds.) *Recherches sur la Chronique de Jean Malalas*, vol. 2, Paris 2006, 97–135; A. Eastmond (ed.), *Viewing Inscriptions in the Late Antique and Medieval World*, Cambridge 2015; A. Avdokhin, ‘Space Oddity? A Praepositus Inscribing Power and Appropriating Cityscapes in Theodosian Constantinople’, *Studies in Byzantine Epigraphy* 1 (2022), 25–54; and an excellent approach to the topic in E. Marlowe, ‘Framing the Sun: The Arch of Constantine and the Roman Cityscape’, *The Art Bulletin* 88 (2006), 223–242.

² See most importantly a number of works by Aude Busine, often utilized by S. in her comments.

The book consists of an introduction which is followed by four chapters and conclusions. At the end of each chapter, we also find a short summary, which helps in following S.'s thoughts. The chapters are usually fitted with catchy titles, e.g. "Epigraphic Unnaming and a Fresh Start." The book is richly illustrated in grayscale photographs, often taken by S. herself during her many research stays in Türkiye.

The Introduction sets the scene for subsequent chapters and gives an outline of the book. S. justifies her choice of temple epigraphy and discusses the traps that may await researchers of the reading of inscriptions, such as the existence of recarved, restored or "forged" inscriptions: e.g., the eulogy of the citizens of Megara who fell fighting Xerxes's armies in 480s BC spuriously attributed to Simonides of Keos but carved only in the fourth or fifth century CE. This part could benefit from a stronger emphasis that recarving or fabricating inscriptions was not just a late antique phenomenon, for example by quoting the multi-layer "founders' oath" from Hellenistic Kyrene, which comprises recarved and possibly edited passages of Archaic inscriptions.³

From the beginning, S. dives deep into tracing cultural parallels or modern counterparts of ancient behaviours, commenting on the plausibility of such comparisons. The Islamic State's attitudes to ancient objects are nicely knitted with a description of the destruction of the temple of Zeus Belos in Apameia by Theodoret, HE 5.21 ("attention sake" rather than religious zeal is argued by S. in both cases, but modern trade of supposedly destroyed antiquities in black markets is not commented). An interesting parallel is certainly Las Vegas as a modern "gambling sanctuary" lavishly decorated with bright neon signs. A digression on the use of inscriptions for the study of literacy levels in antiquity misses references to recent scholarship on private letters from Egypt.⁴

Chapter 1 deals with the "use of real or imagined inscriptions in literature." The key works examined by S. duly include all the major authors notable for the inscriptions which they quoted, among them: Agathias, Kosmas Indikopleustes, Prokopios of Caesarea, and Ioannes Malalas. S. skillfully frames this discussion in the context of transtextuality. She writes about different levels of epigraphic sensitivity of different authors including such major figures as Eusebius or Ammianus who surprisingly had little interest in incorporating epigraphy in their works. S. reconstructs how authors copied, read and understood inscriptions or employed them for their own purposes, how they encountered Archaic Greek alphabets, and how anthologies were created (here, the medieval syllogae of the inscriptions from late antique catacombs of Rome are not recalled). The chapter does not lack examples of misreading or miscontextualizing of old inscriptions, for example through wrong identifications of similarly named emperors or through wishful thinking of ancient authors. The chapter comprises two very extensive passages on inscribed oracles and the importance of inscriptions for the study of hagiography (under a rather anachronistic subtitle "plagiarizing the saints"). The first is a discussion of the famed quotation of the spurious oracle of Apollo at Kyzikos on the arrival of Christianity, preserved in the Tübingen Theosophy. The other – based on the example of the Life of Aberkios commonly believed to be an expanded story line drawn from an Anatolian epitaph. Although S. dedicated a significant portion of the book to this issue, I would gladly see further references to an old theory by Gerhard Ficker that the epitaph described a follower of the

³ IGCyr011000, see also A. J. Graham, 'The Authenticity of the OPKION TON OIKISTHPQN of Cyrene', *The Journal of Hellenic Studies* 80 (1960), 94–111.

⁴ See R. Bagnall, *R. Cribiore, Women's Letters from Ancient Egypt, 300 BC–AD 800*, Ann Arbor 2006 and S. Thorpe, *Daily Life in Ancient Egyptian Personal Correspondence*, Oxford 2021 for earlier periods.

cult described in Lucian's *De Dea Syria* as an brilliant case of modern misreading of inscriptions.⁵ The seminal commentary by Reinhold Merkelbach should also be cited.⁶ On p. 35 note 34 there is a typo in Greek Ἰαμέστη instead of Ἰαμέστη (Dative Greek form of the name Ramesses). On pp. 59–61, the discussion on the exorbitantly high fine from the epitaphs of Aberkios could be better supported by quotations of parallel prices by Jan Iluk (the book is cited only in note 114 without specific pages references).

Chapter 2 deals with the preservations of inscriptions. With the aid of both literary and material sources, S. examines the strategies which late antique Christians adopted while dealing with buildings and inscriptions associated with traditional cults. Among them we find a variety of attitudes which included sparing or just light modifications of non-Christian texts.

The salvage of inscriptions from “obscure places” is prominently discussed in the context of the reuse of statues and inscribed bases at the Embolos Street in Ephesos, and explained through the authority of imperial epigraphy, apparently still highly valued as late as the Theodosian dynasty despite its non-Christian connotations. The “museification” at the Athena’s temple at Priene and the creation of game boards at slabs at Magnesia on the Maeander illustrate other attitudes. On the occasion of analyzing Mylasa, S. introduces the Life of Eusebia. Here I would argue that the main motif behind this narrative is not really the “conflict between ‘worldly’ and ‘heavenly’ concerns” (p. 84) but rather the intention of bishops and male clergy eager to set patterns for a local female monastic community. The text is probably also written by a bishop of Mylasa or on his request.

Further passages describe the layering of official and private inscriptions on buildings, especially the graffiti clustering at Delphi, on the altar of the Chians densely marked by crosses in different sizes and shapes. The practice of adding crosses was introduced earlier in the chapter as an argument that these inscriptions were actually read and understood. Here, further interpretations, such as sealing the evil, are presented. There follows a long discussion of the *Divi Augusti res gestae* at Ankara and possible reasons for its preservations in a relatively good state, including such obviously non-Christian passages such as *theos Sebatos*. We also find an insightful comparison of respecting Christian graffiti and Çavdar graffiti on the temple of Zeus at Aizanoi with an important conclusion that “leaving the ancient Roman texts untouched was a cultural attitude, not a default” (p. 117). While discussing the temples of Palmyra, S. should have stressed that it was a thoroughly reshaped town in Late Antiquity through the eradication of rebellious elites by Aurelian; Aramaic inscriptions should be cited through PAT and Eleonora Cussini’s works. On p. 142 we find a study on „nonsense” marks – in general, I find it questionable that S. discusses masons’ marks and “voces magicae” in the same subchapter as “non-understandable” texts.⁷

Having discussed the reuse of the texts of inscriptions in Christian literature, S. swiftly proceeds to a study of material spolia and physical reuse of inscribed stones in Chapter 3. Due to its nature, the chapter strongly overlaps with research on reuse of architectural elements. It begins with a useful overview of different reasons behind spoliation, as

⁵ G. Ficker, ‘Der heidnische Charakter der Abercius-Inschrift’, *Sitzungsberichte der Königlich-Preußischen Akademie der Wissenschaften zu Berlin* (1894), 87–112.

⁶ R. Merkelbach, ‘Grabepigramm und Vita des Bischofs Aberkios von Hierapolis’, *Epigraphica Anatolica* 28 (1997), 125–139.

⁷ Stonemasons’ marks had their logic which could be disturbed by the relocation of blocks. More research on this will be soon published by Anna Kordas who has examined the marks from the Tauchira Gate in Ptolemais, Cyrenaica, and from other sites in northeastern Africa and Egypt.

presented by modern authors. S. aims to answer if inscribed stones were more carefully treated than others in the spoliation process. At Knidos and Ephesos, she pinpoints cases of indifferent reuse and argues that people in northern parts of the eastern Mediterranean were less sensitive to ascribing a greater value to inscribed blocks. This is, however, not claimed by S. as a “universal law” as she gives a number of examples from Korykos, Sagalassos, Aphrodisias, Baalbek, and Klaros where “active selection” of inscribed pieces was apparently practiced. Regarding the synagogue at Sardis, she argues that reused inscriptions from the Metroon/Kybebe’s temple, also those in the epichoric alphabet and unidentified language, combined with carvings of lions, were meant to stress the heritage of the land and the old Lydian traditions. In conclusions, S. proposes that we have little evidence for “polemical” or “Christian triumphal” reuse of polytheistic inscriptions. On the contrary, where inscriptions were actively selected for reuse, the reason was mostly practical (easily accessible material), pride of the splendid past or aesthetical feelings. In any case, her assessment goes far beyond ascribing just the economic necessity to the reuse of inscriptions. Interestingly, she notices a more relaxed approach of Christians to polytheistic inscriptions than to carved imagery. This, however, is not taken as a presumption that reused inscriptions were not read or properly understood by Christians. The chapter lacks references to the works of Yuri A. Marano on the legal regulations of the spoliation of marble elements.⁸

Chapter 4 introduces the interesting problem of the intentional erasing of inscriptions. The absolute majority of cases discussed here refer to erasure motivated by religious anxiety, though the author is perfectly aware that erasure had a long history in antiquity and was practiced not only for religious reasons. Here, S. frames it as part of “unnaming” polytheistic gods, the change of their ontological status from *theoi* to *daimones* (in the late antique meaning of this word). S. examines different approaches to erasure, among them very gentle adjusting of individual letters, by citing the inscriptions from Aphrodisias where the name of the city was changed to Stauropolis by a careful substitution of only several letters in the original toponym. She also cites the case of Antioch ad Cragum with a dice oracle well preserved except for the names of gods removed from the text. “Indiscriminate erasure” is, on the other hand, introduced regarding the graffiti at the Korykian Cave. This chapter gives S. also several occasions to comment on the “tagging” practice and violence against statues. She notices a similar selective erasure of specific statue parts but concludes that inscriptions triggered less violence than statues. In the discussion of the hiding of non-Christian statues, I missed a reference to the spectacular “treasury of sculptures” unearthed at Tomis/Constanța. Very notably, in the final passages of the chapter, S. devotes a lot of space to reexamine the theory if the copy of *Res Gestae* at Pisidian Antioch was destroyed by Christians but she prudently concludes that we have no solid evidence to support this theory. The chapter also includes interesting remarks on erasures made in the twentieth century.

The final chapter of the book reiterates the main conclusions of the author. S. calls for a more inclusive approaches to studying the act of reading in archaeology. Again, she proves her erudition by an insightful delamination of a poem by Giorgos Seferis based on the epitaphs of Ankara. Here, a useful comparison could be a review of the Alexandrian funerary epigrams by Konstantinos Kavafis, very probably based on real epitaphs. At the end, S.

⁸ E.g., Y. A. Marano, ‘Spoliazione di edifici e reimpiego di materiale da costruzione in età romana: le fonti giuridiche’, in E. Pettenò, F. Rinaldi (eds.), *Memorie dal passato di Iulia Concordia. Un percorso tra le forme del reimpiego e del riuso*, Rome 2011, 140–174.

returns to spolia and stresses the wide character of the book – calling for more studies on non-spoliated architectural elements.

To sum up, I enjoyed reading the book and the skillful combination of the use of both material and written sources by the author. S. is well read in commentaries on literary sources, knowing how to employ them to illuminate the epigraphical or archaeological material, and is well-aware that one cannot always take the claims of ancient authors at face value – a skill which ensured the success of Louis Robert alongside his exceptional erudition of epigraphical texts. An important contribution to the field is the “negative” approach to the study of erasure and re-use through focusing on preserved and untouched objects. Through her work, S. brought to us one of the most interesting studies on the spatial functioning of inscriptions in recent years.

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